

IN THE EYE OF THE PATIENT INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES IN EMOTIONAL REACTIONS TO VISUAL DESIGN AESTHETICS OF HEALTH-CARE PRODUCTS

John Magnus Roos

Veryday

Centre for Consumer Science (CFK) and Department of Business and Administration,
School of Business Economics and Commercial Law, University of Gothenburg

✉ Magnus.roos@veryday.com, Magnus.roos@cfk.gu.se

In memory of Mikael Nevala

ABSTRACT

This study explores how the personality traits of potential patients influence their emotional reactions to the visual design aesthetics of health-care products. Sixty-six students completed a personality test and reported their emotional reactions to thirteen photos of health-care products. The key-findings were (1) a high degree of extraversion influences pleasant affect, (2) a high degree of neuroticism influences unpleasant affect, especially fear, (3) a low degree of conscientiousness influences pleasant affect in terms of positive surprise, (4) a high degree of openness influences happiness, (5) a high degree of extraversion influences fear, while a low degree of extraversion influences sadness (6) a low degree of extraversion, a low degree of neuroticism and/or a high degree of conscientiousness influence the absence of emotional reaction. The study explains why identical products evoke different emotions in different individuals, which is an important step in understanding how different design aesthetics satisfy different individuals based on their personalities.

KEYWORDS: *visceral design, aesthetics, basic emotions, appraisal, personality.*

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, emotional design plays an increasingly important role in creating desire for consumer goods and preferences for commercial messages, and has become a key-driver of consumer value and business value. Rather than goods that are purchased on a consumer market, this study has a somewhat different approach; it focuses on the emotions of people who are exposed to health-care products. The idea is that all of us can, and probably will, end up in a hospital and be exposed to a variety of products that we have not chosen.

Emotions are subjective and individuals differ in their emotional reaction to a given product (Desmet, 2008). It is the personal significance of a product, rather than the product itself, that causes the emotion. Different individuals who appraise the same product in different ways experience different emotions (Desmet, 2010). Personality theorists divide people along such traits as openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. To designers,

this means that no single design will satisfy everyone (Norman, 2004). According to Lewis (2001), it is necessary to take a closer look at individual differences in order to better understand the development of emotions. The aim of this study is to explore if and how personality traits influence emotional reactions to health-care products.

The present study address the questions of whether and how personality traits can contribute to our understanding of emotions, and it discusses how such insights might be relevant for designers. Our theoretical model is based on an appraisal process of fast thinking, basic emotions and personality. Our ambition is to give some psychological contributions to design research, based not only on personality theories, but also on Ekman's 1982 framework of basic emotions and Kahneman's (2011) best seller "Thinking fast and slow." The empirical study and the data analysis are guided by this theoretical framework. The result will be discussed in terms of methodological limitations and related to multidisciplinary research (e.g. neuroscience, psychology, design and marketing) on personality traits and emotions.

AN APPRAISAL PROCESS OF THINKING FAST, BASIC EMOTIONS AND PERSONALITY

Thinking fast

The human brain seems to consist of three different levels, especially relevant for processing information. Firstly, the visceral level, which is automatic and fast. Secondly, the behavioral level, which controls everyday behavior. Thirdly, the reflective level, which is contemplative and thoughtful (Norman, 2004). Chupchik (1999) has a similar perspective and distinguishes between three levels of emotional meanings related to products: sensory/aesthetic, cognitive/behavioral and personal/symbolic. The first level represents sensory qualities that have an immediate effect on experience, the second represents meaning related to performance and ease of use, and the third represents personal meaning beyond product functions and appearance (Chupchik, 1999). Some researchers refer to emotions at the visceral level as “aesthetic” emotions because they are elicited by sensations that are pleasing or displeasing to our senses (Desmet, 2008; Lazarus, 1991). Aesthetic emotions are intrinsic feelings of pleasure or displeasure related to affect disposition, rather than higher-level cognitive processes. Overbeeke and Hekkert (1999) stated that many products or product categories have reached such a level of technical performance that they have become difficult to discriminate on a functional basis:

“Thus, when two coffee makers basically make the same pot of coffee, we take the one that gives us a pleasant, desirable, or inspired feeling” (Overbeeke & Hekkert, 1999, p. 5).

Whereas Norman (2004) argues that appraisal is only involved at the reflective level, Desmet (2008) argues that appraisal can be involved at all three levels of processing. Desmet (2010) distinguishes between three appraisals that, according to him, are universal emotional forces that hide behind all human emotions: (1) a pleasantness appraisal (the extent to which an object provides me pleasantness or pain), (2) a usefulness appraisal (the extent to which a product supports me in reaching my goals), (3) a rightfulness appraisal (the extent to which an object meets or exceeds my standards or expectations). According to Desmet (2010), appealing products correspond to those three basic human forces. In the present study, we will only focus on aesthetic emotions, which we define as pleasantness appraisal on the visceral level.

Kahneman (2011) distinguishes between two systems of processing information: one fast system (i.e. System 1 or the experience self) and one slow system (i.e. System 2 or the remembering/reflecting self). The fast system is impulsive and intuitive; the slow system is reasoning and reflective. The fast system is involved in immediate reactions, based on associations and recognitions. The slow system is involved in processes that demand more cognitive resources, such as monitoring the appropriateness of a behavior in a social situation or comparing two objects for overall value. The fast system

is the one that answers the question: “Does it hurt now?” The slow system is the one that answers the question: “How was it, on the whole? The present study will only focus on the fast system, the experience self. This system is involved in immediate emotional reactions to visual stimuli.

Basic emotions

Norman’s (2004) three levels of processing information, discussed above, reflect the evolution of the brain, starting with primitive one-celled organisms, primarily driven by the visceral level and slowly evolving to more complex animals, to vertebrates, mammals and finally, apes and humans. During evolution, basic emotions have played an important role in determining which species survive (Darwin, 1872; Ekman & Friesen, 2003). According to Ekman and Friesen (2003), the six basic emotions are: anger, fear, disgust, sadness, surprise and happiness. Basic emotions are universally recognized and universally expressed through facial expressions. When people from different cultures viewed photographs showing facial expressions of basic emotions, they had little difficulty identifying the emotion that each expression conveyed (Ekman, 1982). Such emotions are pure and not amenable to deconstructions. Basic emotions are relevant for this study, because they appear on the visceral level (Norman, 2004) and belong to such automatic activities that are attributed to the “thinking fast” system (Kahneman, 2011). Such emotions help us make quick decisions about what is good or bad, safe or dangerous, and send appropriate signals to other parts of our brain and body. This is the start of affective processing (Norman, 2004).

Personality

Despite the evidence that basic emotions seem to be universal (Ekman & Friesen, 2003), people may differ in their emotional reactions toward a specific object. Losing a loved one might be expressed in a number of ways: by openly crying and wailing (e.g. sadness), by anger and irritation (e.g. anger), by singing and dancing (e.g. happiness) or by silence and isolation (e.g. absence of emotion) (Atkinson et al., 2000). We have good reason to believe that emotional reactions of basic emotions also differ when responding to stimuli that in general might elicit less dramatic reactions, such as health-care products. Previous research (i.e. Desmet, 2008; Hong & Lee, 2010; Lau-Gesk & Myers-Levy, 2009) has shown that the appraisal process is related to several psychological factors, such as personal goals, moods, imagination, empathy, cognitive capacity and motivation. All such factors are highly subjective and might therefore differ between individuals.

Distinctions among individuals receive considerable support from an increasingly extensive amount of psychological literature on personality (Larsen & Buss, 2005). Personality is an individual’s particular combination of feelings (i.e. emotions), thoughts (i.e. cognitions) and behavior (Larsen & Buss, 2005; Lewis, 2001). The framework that has received the most attention and support from personality researchers

is the five-factor model, which was originally coined by Fiske (1949). During the 50s, 60s and 70s, several independent research teams took slightly different routes, yet all arrived at the same conclusions – most human personality traits can be boiled down into five broad dimensions of personality traits, regardless of language and culture (Larsen & Buss, 2005). The five-factor model has been empirically tested in every decade since 1949, suggesting that the structure is also replicable over time. In scientific spheres, the five-factor model is nowadays the most widely accepted and used model of personality (Holmberg & Weibull, 2010). According to Larsen and Buss (2005), key markers of the five-factor model are as follows:

- Openness (versus reticence). Open people are open to innovation, different cultures, new information and the emotions of other people. Reticent people are more conservative and reserved to innovations, cultures, information and social emotions.
- Conscientiousness (versus spontaneity). Conscientious people are forward thinking and plan their lives. Spontaneous people are more impulsive and act on the spur of the moment.
- Extraversion (versus introversion). Extravert people have a great impact on their social environment and tend to be happy. Introvert people are more quiet and tend to be more like wallflowers.
- Agreeableness (versus antagonistic). Agreeable people negotiate to resolve conflicts and strive for agreement. Antagonistic people are aggressive, assert their power to resolve social conflicts and seem to get themselves into a lot of social conflicts.
- Neuroticism (versus emotional stability). Neurotic people have a variability of moods over time, are anxious, stressed and disconnected from life and other people. Emotionally stable people are more composed, relaxed and tend to be like boats that remain on course through choppy waters.

Theorizing

In this study, we view the appraisal process for emotional reactions as a fast and immediate reactions rather than a slow process of cognitive elaborations. According to Lau-Gesk and Meyers-Levy (2009), such a perspective is more appropriate for emotions that demand less cognitive resources (e.g. basic, univalent and non-self-conscious emotions) than for emotions that demand more cognitive resources (e.g. complex, mixed and self-conscious emotions). When individuals do not have the ability (or motivation) to engage in the appraisal process, they can be said to have a neutral appraisal (Ruckler et al., in press). In our basic model, we use photos of health-care products as stimuli, personality traits as independent variables, and basic emotions and neutral as dependent variables (Figure 1). As set out in the methodology, we will control the stimuli in order to investigate the effect of personality traits on emotions.

Figure 1. Model of product emotion (Inspired by Desmet & Hekkert, 2001).

METHOD

Experimental design

This study was based on an experiment conducted with student samples. The controlled stimuli in this experiment were 13 photos of health-care products designed by the Swedish design agency Veryday. All products were designed for multinational companies (e.g. AstraZeneca, Iirras, Maquet, Pfizer and Roche) and are experienced by patients around the world on a daily basis (Appendix). The specific products were selected together with designers at Veryday to represent the huge variety of emotional design in the life-science business. The inclusion criteria of products were the following: (i) The products should be intended for all adults (not especially designed for specific genders or ages), (ii) the product should still exist in hospital contexts and be the latest version, (iii) the product should be used when interacting with patients who are conscious (not under anesthesia).

Participants

Sixty-six undergraduate students participated in the study. In order to capture heterogeneous personalities, data were collected from two different student samples. The first sample consisted of 3rd year marketing students at the School of Business, Economics and Law at the University of Gothenburg (n=39). Data from this sample were collected on the 20th of January 2014. The second sample consisted of 1st and 2nd year design students at the University College of Art, Crafts and Design in Stockholm (n=27) and data from this sample were collected on the 23rd of January 2014. Fifty-two per-

cent of the participants were women ($n=34$) and forty-eight percent were men ($n=32$). The mean age was twenty-five years ($M=24.8$). The average number of days that the participants spent in hospital during their lifetimes was six ($M=6.1$). All participants were able to communicate in Swedish and 94 percent ($n=62$) were Swedish citizens.

Procedure

The study consisted of two parts: Firstly, participants filled in their background information and completed a personality test individually (approximately 10 minutes). Secondly, participants observed 13 photos of health-care products together on a large screen (Figure 2) and reported their emotions individually (approximately 10 minutes). For each photo, participants were told to report the emotion that best corresponded to their feeling. Participants were told to report the emotion as they experienced it and to use their gut-feeling. They were also told to report their emotions even if they could not identify the object or its usability. After each photo, a white screen was shown for 10 seconds, in order to neutralize the spill-over between photos. As will be discussed below, the emotions were reported through a combined verbal and visual self-report scale. The respondents were told to primarily focus on the visual self-report measure.

Instrument

The questionnaire covered areas such as background data (e.g. age, gender, citizenship, number of days in hospital), personality traits and emotional reactions to each product respec-

Figure 2. Participants at University College of Arts, Crafts and Design.

tively. The personality traits were measured through the HP5 inventory, a short version of the five-factor model especially adjusted for well-being and health-care studies (Gustavsson, Jönsson, Linder & Weinryb, 2003). Table 1 illustrates the link between personality traits and the specific items in HP5i. The scale used for each item was a four-level scale; completely agree (coded as 1), partly agree (coded as 2), partly disagree (coded as 3), completely disagree (coded as 4).

The emotional reaction to each photo was measured through a combined verbal and visual self-report measure. The visual self-report measure is based on photographs of universal facial expressions of basic emotions (Ekman & Friesen, 2003)

PERSONALITY TRAIT	ITEMS IN HP5
Openness (reverse scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I think emotions many times are exaggerated • I often have difficulties to understand other's feelings • Normally, I avoid getting involved in others problem • I do not analyze my feelings
Conscientiousness (reverse scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I usually act on the spur of the moment • I often throw myself too hastily into things • I usually talk before I think • I am an impulsive person
Extraversion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I often feel exhilarated • I usually enjoy life • I am usually in a good mood when I socialize • I am keen on trying out new things
Agreeableness (reverse scale)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I often make sarcastic commentaries • I usually behave vengefully if I am treated badly • I usually come up with piercing and malicious answers • Someone who offends me, can count on trouble
Neuroticism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I often feel uncomfortable and ill at ease • I often feel pressure when I have to speed up • I often have muscles so tense that I get tired • Unexpected noise makes me jump

Table 1. Link between personality traits and items
Source: Gustavsson et al, 2003

Figure 3. Verbal and visual emotions used in the self-report measure.

	Sadness	Anger	Fear	Disgust	Positive surprise	Happiness	Neutral	Pleasant affect	Unpleasant affect
Openness (r)	0.02	0.09	0.25	-0.19	0.25	-0.79*	-0.06	-0.16	0.16
Conscientiousness (r)	0.01	0.50	0.14	0.24	0.63**	-0.19	-0.41**	0.33*	0.19
Extraversion	-0.93*	0.19	0.80**	0.27	0.58	0.35	-0.62**	0.58*	0.29
Agreeableness (r)	-0.15	0.00	-0.24	0.26	-0.22	0.00	0.18	-0.09	-0.14
Neuroticism	-0.37	0.36	0.38*	0.38	0.00	0.19	-0.34*	0.10	0.29*
Intercept	1.22	-6.82*	-5.48**	-5.14**	-5.53**	-2.28	3.46**	-3.91**	-2.79**
Nagelkerke R ²	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.01

Table 2. The relationship between personality traits and emotional reactions. (Binominal logistic regression. Log odds)
 Note. $p < 0.01$: **; $p < 0.05$: *. r = reversal. n = 766. Pleasant affect = positive surprise + happiness. Unpleasant affect = sadness + anger + fear + disgust.

and constructed together with designers at Veryday in Sweden (Figure 3).

Data analysis

Several logistic regression analyses were performed with a certain basic emotion, neutral or affect as dependent variables and the five personality traits as independent variables. The affect variables were constructed through the basic emotions, which means that the sum of positive surprise and happiness were used to construct a pleasant affect and that the sum of sadness, fear, disgust and anger were used to construct an unpleasant affect. A total of 766 pictures were analyzed in each logistic regression, based on reactions from 66 persons.

Findings

The key-findings are (1) a high degree of extraversion influences the experience of a more pleasant affect; (2) a high degree of neuroticism influences the experience of a more unpleasant affect, especially fear; (3) a low degree of conscientiousness influences the experience of a pleasant affect in terms of positive surprise; (4) a high degree of openness

influences the experience of happiness; (5) a high degree of extraversion influences the experience of fear, while a low degree of extraversion influences the experience of sadness; (6) a low degree of extraversion, a low degree of neuroticism and/or a low degree of conscientiousness influence the absence of emotional experience, neutral (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

Methodological considerations

The present study has a number of methodological limitations that might be related to each other. Firstly, the study was conducted in an unnatural context: a classroom where students were told to emotionally respond to photos of healthcare products. Real life experiences most often involve multiple and interrelated emotions that evolve and interact with each other, with the event at hand, and with our reactions to these events (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012). Secondly, the study only focused on basic and univalent emotions (compared to complex and mixed emotions). In the present study, our focus was on aesthetic emotions with appraisals in terms of intrinsic pleasantness, rather than more complex emotions (e.g. instrumental and social emotions) with usefulness and

rightfulness appraisals (Desmet, 2003; 2010). However, there are most likely more emotions that could have been characterized as aesthetic emotions than the six basic emotions of Ekman (1982) used here. With the use of PrEmo for instance, participants are able to express blends of 14 distinct emotional reactions through a non-verbal measure (Desmet, Overbeeke & Tax, 2001). Thirdly, the study only focused on measuring emotions in the moment (compared to reflections and memories). This implies that our findings relate to the experience self rather than the remembering self (Kahneman, 2011), and should be applied to appearance in visceral design rather than self-conscious emotions (e.g. proud, guilt) in reflective design (Norman, 2004; Lau-Gesk & Meyers-Levy, 2009).

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Personality traits, positive emotions and pleasant affect

We found that three traits are associated with positive emotions and/or pleasant affect: (1) a high degree of extraversion, (2) a high degree of openness and (3) a low degree of conscientiousness (i.e. more impulsive). Our first finding corresponds to previous research, which has found that a high degree of extraversion is associated to subjective well-being and pleasant affect (Diener & Lucas, 1999; Larsen & Buss, 2005). Our second finding also corresponds to previous research. A higher degree of openness is often slightly positively correlated with a pleasant affect (i.e. happiness), although the relationship between openness and a pleasant affect is much weaker than the relationship between extraversion and a pleasant affect (Diener & Lucas, 1999; Larsen & Buss, 2005). In the present study, we have found that openness influences happiness rather than positive surprise. It might be that individuals with a high degree of openness are more open to sudden impulses, which makes them less surprised. Our third finding is more unexpected. To the best of our knowledge, the relationship between positive surprise and impulsivity, in the moment, has not previously been explored. What we know from advertising research is that individuals in need of a high degree of control are difficult to persuade through simple emotional appeals, compared to individuals that require a lower degree of control (Morales, Wu & Fitzsimons, 2012). This might support our finding that impulsive individuals respond more emotionally than other individuals, but not particularly why they respond with a pleasant affect. Ramathan and Williams (2007) have found that prudent individuals (i.e. conscientious) focus more on problems while impulsive individuals focus more on hedonic pleasure. The combination of these two studies (Morales, Wu & Fitzsimons, 2012; Ramathan & Williams, 2007) gives some support to our finding: that impulsive people respond more frequently with pleasant affect compared to people in general. However, we have not found any support from previous research for why individuals respond with positive surprise rather than happiness. It might be because surprise refers to a sudden and unexpected

increase of arousal (Apter, 2007). According to Desmet (2008), positive surprise (i.e. astonishment) has a higher arousal than happiness (i.e. joyfulness). Impulsivity has been associated with thrill and novelty seeking; for instance, in experimenting with drugs (Castellanos-Ryan & Conrod, 2012) and in compulsive buying (Sun, Wu & Youn, 2004). The higher level of arousal might therefore explain why positive surprise, rather than happiness, is related to lack of impulse control. The pleasant affect might appear in the moment, as we measure here, but does not need to cause more pleasant affect in total, when long-term effects are included.

Personality traits, negative emotions and unpleasant affect

We have found that negative emotions and/or unpleasant affect are related to neuroticism and extraversion. The first finding, the relation between a high degree of neuroticism and a negative reaction to visual stimuli is well known and well documented (Diener & Lucas, 1999; Larsen & Buss, 2005; Canli et al., 2001; Fox, Ridgewell & Ashwin, 2009). Fox (2012), explains the relationship between neuroticism and fear through neurobiological mechanisms, so-called serotonin transporter genes; “People with a short form of serotonin transporter gene have an emergency brain that reacts much more vigorously to danger” (Fox, 2012, p. 111). The second finding is more interesting and might be provocative for some personality theorists. This finding questions one of the most fundamental principles in the five-factor model of personality: that extraversion relates to the pleasant affect, but not to the unpleasant affect (Costa & McCrae, 1980). If we limit our scope to only measuring the unpleasant affect, our finding corresponds to previous research (Table 2). However, several researchers (i.e. Desmet, 2008; Russel, 1980) argue that the unpleasant affect is too broad a concept and thus propose more distinct emotions, based on an individual’s level of arousal. Fear, for instance, has a much higher arousal than sadness. The present study shows that extraversion is related to distinct emotions of the unpleasant affect; a high degree of extraversion influences fear, while a low degree of introversion influences sadness. This finding has high construct validity because it is in line with the theoretical ideas behind the trait under consideration: extraversion. Extroverts are more vigorous and active than introverts and therefore experience the unpleasant affect with a high degree of arousal (i.e. fear), while introverts are more quiet and calm than extroverts and therefore experience the unpleasant affect with a low degree of arousal (i.e. sadness).

Personality traits and the absence of emotions and affects

We found that a low degree of neuroticism, a low degree of extraversion and a high degree of conscientiousness influence the absence of emotional reaction (i.e. neutral). In contrast to many previous studies (i.e. Costa & McCrae, 1980; Canli et al., 2001) on positive and negative reactions to stimuli, this study allowed a “neutral” response alternative. However, our

findings are not very spectacular. According to previous research, a high degree of extraversion and a high degree of neuroticism are the personality traits that have been most closely related to emotion and affect (Diener & Lucas, 1999). If those traits are low (as for introverts and/or emotionally stable people), the probability for a neutral response should increase, which corresponds to our findings (Table 2). The relationship between a high degree of conscientiousness and a neutral response is less explored. This finding corresponds to our previous discussion regarding conscientious people; individuals that desire self-control are more difficult to persuade through simple emotional appeals (Morales, Wu & Fritzimons, 2012). To the best of our knowledge, no previous study has found that individuals with a low degree of neuroticism, a low degree of extraversion and/or a high degree of conscientiousness are particularly emotional in their reactions to stimuli in psychometric self-rating scales or in neurobiological measures, such as fMRI (Costa & McCrae, 1980; Canli et al., 2001; Fox, Ridgewell & Ashwin, 2009). With regards to the theoretical ideas behind openness, as well as the measurement items, we found it surprising that people with a low degree of openness did not respond more neutrally. One explanation might be that the health-care products used in this study are not very emotional. According to Moore, Harris and Chen (1995), people with a high degree of affect intensity respond more strongly only when it comes to affective ads, not neutral ads. A related explanation might be that photos of health-care products in a classroom seldom evoke mixed emotions (although it is hard to know as we did not allow multiple responses). Previous research (Hong & Lee, 2010) has found that people with a high degree of openness (i.e. a high degree of abstract thinking) are literally more open for processing and responding positively to appeals with mixed emotions (Hong & Lee, 2010; Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012). An alternative explanation might be that people with a high degree of openness respond with positive emotions when they experience mixed emotions, while people with a low degree of openness do not explore mixed emotions to the same degree, and therefore more easily respond with a univalenced emotion, either pleasant or unpleasant.

Implication for designers

Norman (2004) stated that personality traits are important for designers to consider because they will influence whether a person will be satisfied by a certain product or not:

“Personality theories divide people along such dimensions as extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, emotional stability, and openness. To designers, this means that no single design will satisfy everyone”. (Norman, 2004, p. 39).

It is worth noting that Norman uses the terminology “satisfy”, an instrumental emotion related to goal compliance, and a reflective and overall judgment of the design object, rather than an aesthetic emotion in the moment of experiencing. However, elsewhere Norman (2004) discusses personality traits in relation to aesthetic emotions. According to him, such emotions help people to make fast decisions regarding what is good or

bad, safe or dangerous, and send appropriate signals to other parts of our brain and body, and thereby start the whole system of affective processing. An injection *in the eye of the patient* [Appendix, Picture 7] might be a very emotional experience. If designers know that health-care products evoke more fear in some patients than others, they can make sure that they recruit appropriate candidates for the user studies. If designers are able to reduce fear appeals among patients with a high degree of neuroticism by addressing product design, they are probably also able to reduce it for all other patients, which is in line with arguments related to Design for all/Inclusive design/Universal design. Truly understanding the needs of all users, guaranteeing input from all types of individuals (even those that are not so explicit), set the foundation for a greater match between user needs and product success.

It is worth remembering that researchers first started to be interested in emotions because emotions were perceived to have survival values for species (Darwin, 1872). In certain kinds of contexts, small stimuli might have a huge impact and greater meaning. An experience of fear in a hospital might imply the end is near.

In recent years, modern health care systems have become more personalized, preventive and proactive. This is in line with the results of this study, which show that on an emotional level, users react differently to health-care stimuli depending on their personality. However, the challenge is to design a health care system that can actually respond differently to different patient personalities. The possibility to adjust health-care products to individual needs and desires might be restricted for a number of reasons (e.g. financial, market structure, competitors, business and political priorities, etc.). In practice, it is more realistic to provide individually adjusted services within the realm of digital health-care, rather than products. We suggest more research in this field, to find out how personality is related to the needs and desires in interactive and digital health care service systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author is greatly indebted to Riksbankens Jubileumsfond in Stockholm for providing funding. The author would also like to thank colleges at Veryday for the 13 stimuli products, the visual self-report measure and fruitful discussions.

REFERENCES

- Apter, M. (2007). *Reveral Theory: The Dynamics of Motivation, Emotion and Personality*. Oxford, UK: Oneworld.
- Atkinson, R. L., Atkinson, R. C., Smith, E. E., Bem, D. J., Nolen-Hoeksema, S. (2000). *Hilgard's Introduction to Psychology*. New York: Harcourt College Publishers.
- Canli, T., Zhao, Z., Desmond, J. E., Kang, E. J., Gross, J., Gabrieli, J. D. E. (2001). An fMRI Study of Personality Influences on Brain Re-activity on Emotional Stimuli. *Behavioural Neuroscience*, 115, 33-42.

- Castellanos-Ryan, N., Conrod, P. (2012). Personality and Substance Misuse: Evidence for a four-factor model of vulnerability. In: J. C. Verster, K. Brady, M. Galanter, P. Conrod (Eds.) *Drug Abuse and Addiction in Medical Illness: Causes, consequences and treatment*, p. 47-62. New York, NY: Springer.
- Costa, P. T., McCrae, R. R. (1980). Influence of Extraversion and Neuroticism on Subjective Well-being: Happy and unhappy people. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 38, 668-678.
- Cupchik, G. C. (1999). Emotion and Industrial Design: Reconciling meanings and feelings. In C. J. Overbeeke, P. Hekkert (Eds.) *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Design and Emotion*, 3-5 November, Delft, the Netherlands, 75-82.
- Darwin, C. (1872). *The Expression of Emotion in Man and Animal*. New York, NY: Philosophical Library.
- Desmet, P. M. A. (2003). A Multi-layered Model of Product Emotions, *The Design Journal*, 6, 4-13.
- Desmet, P. M. A. (2008). Product emotion. In H. N. J. Schifferstien, P. Hekkert (Eds.), *Product Experiences*, p. 379-397. Amsterdam, NL: Elsevier.
- Desmet, P. M. A. (2010). *Three Levels of Product Emotions. Proceedings of International Conference on Kansei Engineering and Emotion Research*, 2-4 March, Paris, France.
- Desmet, P. M. A., Hekkert, P. (2001). The Basis of Product Emotions. In P. Jordan and W. S. Green (Eds.), *Proceedings of Pleasure Based Human Factors Conference*, 11-13 April, Copenhagen. Denmark.
- Desmet, P., Overbeeke, K., Tax, S. (2001). Designing Products with Added Emotional Value: Development and application of an approach for research through design. *The design journal*, 1, 32-47
- Diener, E., Lucas, R. (1999). Personality and Subjective Well-being. In D. Kahneman, E. Diener, N. Schwarz (Eds.) *Well-being: The foundation of hedonic psychology*, p. 213-229. New York, NY: Russel Sage Foundation.
- Ekman, P. (1982). *Emotions in the Human Face*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Ekman, P., Friesen, W. V. (2003). *Unmasking the Face. A guide to recognizing emotions from facial expressions*. Cambridge, MA: Malor Books.
- Fiske, D. W. (1949). Consistency of the Factorial Structures of Personality Ratings from Different Sources, *Journal of abnormal and social psychology*, 44, 329-344.
- Fokkinga, S., Desmet, P. (2012). Meaningful Mix or Tricky Conflict? A categorization of mixed emotional experience and their usefulness for design. *Proceedings of 8th International Design and Emotion Conference*, 11-14 September, London, England..
- Fox, E. (2012). *Rainy Brain, Sunny Brain: The new science of optimism and pessimism*. London, UK: William Heinemann.
- Fox, E., Ridgewell, A., Ashwin, C. (2009). Looking on the Bright Side: Biased attention and the human serotonin transporter gene. *Proceedings of the Royal Society: Biological Science*, 276, 1747-1751.
- Gustavsson, J. P., Jönsson, E. G., Linder, J., Weinryb, R. M. (2003). The HP5 Inventory: Definition and assessment of five health-relevant personality traits from a five-factor model perspective. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 35, 69-89.
- Holmberg, S., Weibull, L. (2010). Människans fem personlighetsegenskaper. In S. Holmberg and L. Weibull. (Eds.) *Nordiskt ljus*, p. 323-328. Gothenburg, SE: SOM Institute, University of Gothenburg.
- Hong, J. W. & Lee, A. Y. (2010). Feeling Mixed but Not Torn: The moderating role of construal level in mixed emotions appeal. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37, 456-472.
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, Fast and Slow*. New York, NY: Allen Lane.
- Larsen, R. J., Buss, D. M. (2005). *Personality Psychology: Domain of knowledge about human nature*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
- Lau-Gesk, L., Meyers-Levy, J. (2009). Emotional Persuasion: When the valence versus the resource demands of emotions influence consumer's attitudes. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 36, 585-599.
- Lazarus, R. S. (1991). Progress on a Cognitive-Motivational-Relational Theory of Emotion. *American Psychologist*, 46, 819-834.
- Lewis, M. D. (2001). Personal Pathways in the Development of Appraisal: A complex system/stage theory perspective. In K. R. Scherer, A. Schorr, T. Johnstone (Eds.) *Appraisal Processes in Emotion: Theory, methods, research*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press, 205-220.
- Moore, D. J., Harris, W. D., Chen, H. C. (1995). Affect Intensity: An individual difference response to advertising appeals. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 22, 154-164.
- Morales, A. C., Wu, E. C., Fitzsimons, G. J. (2012). How Disgust Enhances the Effectiveness of Fear Appeals. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 49, 383-393.
- Norman, D.A. (2004) *Emotional Design: Why we Love (or Hate) Everyday Things*. New York, NY: Basic Books
- Overbeeke, C. J., Hekkert, P. (1999). In C. J. Overbeeke, P. Hekkert (Eds.) *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Design and Emotion*, 3-5 November, Delft, the Netherlands, 5-6.
- Ramathan, S., Williams, P. (2007). Immediate and Delayed Emotional Consequences of Indulgence: The moderating influence of personality type on mixed emotions. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 34, 212-223.
- Rucker, D. D., Tormala, Z. L., Petty, R. E., Brinol, P. (in press). Consumer Conviction and Commitment: An appraisal-based framework for attitude certainty. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*.
- Russel, J. A. (1980). A Circumplex Model of Affect. *Journal of Personal and Social Psychology*, 39, 1161-1178.
- Sun, T. Wu, G., Youn, S. (2004). Psychological Antecedents of Impulsive and Compulsive Buying: A hierarchical perspective. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 30, 143-153.

APPENDIX – PHOTOS OF HEALTH CARE PRODUCTS

Picture 1

Picture 2

Picture 3

Picture 4

Picture 5

Picture 6

Picture 7

Picture 8

Picture 9

Picture 10

Picture 11

Picture 12

Picture 13